

REVIEW ON PLASTIC WASTE PYROLYSIS: A PROMISING PATHWAY OF FUEL GENERATION AND RENEWABLE ENERGY

Md. Hafijur Rahman Sabbir*¹, Md. Asif All Azad², Tasnim Zahan³

¹ Undergraduate student, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Bangladesh, e-mail:

sabbir.hafijur.rahman@gmail.com

² Undergraduate student, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Bangladesh, e-mail:

asif.che.kuet@gmail.com

³ Undergraduate student, Khulna University of Engineering & Technology, Bangladesh, e-mail:

zahan2229027@stud.kuet.ac.bd

***Corresponding Author**

Abstract

Plastic is a useful substance due to its affordability, durability, and resilience, among other qualities. Hydrocarbons polymerize to form plastic. Plastic is produced at a rate of about 1.3 billion metric tons per year to meet world consumption demand. Waste plastic is a significant worry for everyone since it takes decades to disintegrate. On the other hand, as urbanization and industrialization continue to grow, so does the global need for fossil fuels. Finding alternatives to traditional fuels has become extremely necessary in today's world. Since plastics are petroleum-based, the rise in their usage has influenced the demand for non-renewable fossil fuels. Pyrolysis oil has a high calorific value and, hence, potential as an alternative fuel. Converting plastics to gasoline is a possible solution to both of these issues. At high temperatures (>370°C) and without oxygen, pyrolysis is a thermochemical degradation of organic materials that occurs. Pyrolysis oil, carbon black, and hydrocarbons are all products of this process. The present study reviewed 164 research articles that specifically addressed plastics' thermal and catalytic degradation through pyrolysis. The primary objective of this study is to explore the various factors that influence the end products of this process, particularly the production of oil, gaseous by-products, and char. This study attempts to conduct a contrasting investigation of the yields produced through thermal and catalytic pyrolysis processes that are carried out on various categories of plastics. Additionally, this review discussed the qualities of liquid fuel and several approaches to optimizing liquid oil production.

Keywords: Plastics; wastes; fuel; pyrolysis; hydrocarbons

1. Introduction

Plastic is a polymer with a large molecular weight that was discovered by Alexander Parkes in 1862 [1]. Carbon is the sole or predominant constituent element in the high-molecular chain that comprises polymers. In the industry, "plastics" refers to a broad category of materials, including polymers and resins that are composed entirely or partially of carbon combined with oxygen, hydrogen, nitrogen, and other organic or inorganic elements. It can be molded into many forms through the application of either separately or in combination with heat and pressure. Plastics are classified by the Society of Plastic Industry (SPI) using an identifying code system based on their chemical structure and intended application, which makes it easier to recycle waste plastic. These classifications include HDPE (High-Density Polyethylene), LDPE (Low-Density Polyethylene), PET (Polyethylene Terephthalate), PVC (Polyvinyl Chloride), PP (Polypropylene), PS (Polystyrene) and Others [2].

Plastics have several applications because of their light weight, durability, and versatility. The variety of plastic applications has led to a rise in plastic usage. As a result, plastic garbage is increasing daily. The annual global production of traditional plastics is estimated to reach around 400 million tons, of which half of this waste is either recycled or dumped in landfills [3]. Over 15 million metric tonnes of garbage are estimated to be dumped into the ocean yearly [4]. Plastic waste finds its way into the ocean in several ways. Two-thirds of the debris comes from land-based sources, including rubbish that washes on beaches and litter deposited in towns and cities. Wet wipes, plastic bottles, cotton swabs, and other personal hygiene products comprise most waste items. The US plastic incineration industry released 5.9 million metric tonnes of CO₂ in 2015 and is expected to reach 49 million metric tonnes by 2030 and an estimated 91 million metric tonnes by the end of this century [5]. As a result, incinerating rubbish releases a multitude of toxic substances causing adverse effects on the health of anyone residing in close range to the incinerators.. Compared to incineration, landfilling has a far lesser environmental effect [6]. However, landfills are now at capacity, and there is no more room for garbage to accumulate worldwide. Landfilling pollutes the land and water supply, as well as having an impact on animals. Plastic manufacturing and usage pose a significant environmental risk due to the long-lasting decomposition period of plastic materials.

2. Literature Review

Pyrolysis is the degradation of plastic polymers by heating in a lack of oxygen, creating gaseous and fluid products, which may be exploited as fuels [7]. When plastics are thermally decomposed, free radicals of a smaller size are produced, and these stable molecules include paraffinic compounds, isoparaffinic compounds, olefins, naphthene, and aromatics [7]. In an experiment to understand the characteristics of pyrolysis oil, burning organic matter in an oven yielded pyrolysis oil and a mixture of gases and carbon black. In this experiment, oil was produced using plastic waste with the use of "Aluminum silicate" catalyst, which resulted in excellent similarities with pure fuel oils [8]. Another study conducted pyrolysis of plastic waste at 900°C and found a green liquid fuel with an increased calorific value at this higher temperature than 425°C [9]. A study on the thermal pyrolysis of plastic waste for the production of liquid fuel involved the use of a chamber, condenser, batch, and semi-batch fuel storage. This process resulted in the generation of oil, petroleum, char, diesel, and liquid fuel [10]. In another study, pyrolysis oil was extracted from waste plastic, producing 1.65 liters of oil from 1.5 kg of plastics [11]. In an investigation, the conversion of waste plastic into fuel oil was done by catalytic pyrolysis with findings indicating that the resulting gasoline was compatible with sustainable environmental practices, also offering enhanced fuel economy and effective control over harmful emissions [12].

2.1 Thermal Pyrolysis

Waste plastics are pyrolyzed in thermal pyrolysis by heating them at elevated temperatures in the absence of oxygen to decompose them [13]. The thermal pyrolysis process is governed by radical chain reactions, proliferation, and transfer of free radicals, along with chain-scission and termination of the primary chain [14, 15, 16, 17]. There are three types of pyrolysis products: non-condensable gas, liquid oil (including paraffins, olefins, naphthene, and aromatics), and solid debris [15, 18, 19]. Because of the vast range of low-value hydrocarbons produced by thermal cracking, the end products might range from hydrogen to coke. Thermal pyrolysis produces more non-condensable gaseous portions and less liquid fuel like diesel [20]. This process yields a large number of oligomers by transferring hydrogen from the polymer chain's tertiary carbon atom to the radical site [19]. Polypropylene (PP) is the least susceptible to heat cracking due to its high tertiary carbon concentration, followed by HDPE (high-density polyethylene) and LDPE (low-density polyethylene) [15]. Two radicals are produced due to a homolytic break in the carbon-carbon bond, either at the chain's end via a breaking or at random [21, 22]. When it comes to PP and PE, the chain splits at random [22]. Secondary radicals are formed as a result of intra- and intermolecular hydrogen transfer processes. In the presence of terminal radicals and/or fresh radicals, it may produce molecules that are saturated or unsaturated. Experiment conditions alter intramolecular and intermolecular hydrogen transfer, leading to a rise in olefin production while a decrease in the production of paraffin in the second phase [16, 21, 22]. A representation of the thermal pyrolysis process has been illustrated in the Fig. 1 [23].

Fig. 1: A diagram of a thermal pyrolysis facility

Termination reactions include disproportionation reactions, that produce various alkanes and olefins or a combination of radicals, which can create the same products. When two secondary radicals or a secondary radical and a primary radical interact, branched products of hydrocarbons distributed in the C₅-C₈₀ range are generated

[21, 22]. At high temperatures, a large amount of hydrogen is created. Thermal cracking products are of limited economic worth, primarily if used as fuel [21]. In this technique, getting a wide variety of outputs is challenging, and operational temperature requires between 500 to 900 °C [24]. Because of these limitations, recovering the fundamental components from waste plastic is costlier in thermal pyrolysis.

2.2 Catalytic Pyrolysis

The limited heat conductivity of polymers necessitates high temperatures for the thermal pyrolysis process [15]. Applying catalytic pyrolysis is a potential solution to lessen the high heat requirement. Catalytic pyrolysis can be used as a replacement for recycling pure or mixed plastic waste [25].

The catalyst can accelerate:

- Low-temperature breakdown processes with reduced power consumption [21, 26–28];
- Decreased expenditures and prevention of the generation of potentially harmful by-products [21, 29];
- Maximize the productive capacity that has a more significant economic benefit [15, 28, 30];
- Boost the degree of selectivity of the procedure [19, 27];
- More rapid cracking reactions, which ultimately result in shorter residence durations and reactors with low loads [21];
- Products with reduced boiling point range [31];

The polymer cracking process employs both homogeneous and heterogeneous catalyst systems. Heterogeneous catalysts have been more often utilized because of the simplicity with which they may be separated and recovered [21, 27]. To speed up the catalytic reaction in homogeneous systems, Lewis acids (such as AlCl_3) and fused metal tetrachloroaluminates ($\text{M}(\text{AlCl}_4)_n$) are used, in which M represents the metal to be used, and n can be either 1 or 2, are frequently used [21].

Heterogeneous catalysts such as nanocrystalline zeolites (such as n-HZSM-5), mesostructured catalysts (such as MCM-41), silica-alumina, alumina, and FCC (Fluid Catalytic Cracking) catalysts are often employed as solid acid catalysts [15, 21, 27, 32]. Zeolites can enhance the quality of products by being used in the pyrolysis of polyethylene and other polymers. This is because their acidity and crystalline microporous structure (textural characteristics) make it easier for hydrogen transfer processes to occur, resulting in high gas conversion rates within the temperature range of 350°C to 500°C [14, 19, 33–35]. Due to these inherent characteristics, catalytic pyrolysis has the potential for operation at reduced temperatures and shortened reaction periods in comparison to thermal pyrolysis [32]. The Fig. 2 shows the process of catalytic pyrolysis [31].

Chemical properties such as strength and acidic sites impact the activity of these catalyst materials. Solid structural parameters such as specific surface area, particle size, and pore size distribution are also critical to their effectiveness because they regulate access to large polyolefin molecules at the catalytically active locations within the structure [29, 37]. The process of breakdown may be influenced by impurities and chemical alterations that take place inside the polymer structure during use. However, the majority of studies on the catalytic degradation of polymers is conducted using pure materials. [14–16, 36]. The more acidic sites in the polyolefin pyrolysis, the more catalytic activity there is. Hence, zeolite catalysts increase acid conversion rates compared to non-zeolitic catalysts [36]. The formation of carbonium ions is affected by the presence of acidic sites on catalysts in three distinct manners: by increasing the density and strength of these acid sites via the hydrogen transfer processes during oligomerization/alkylation and aromatization reactions. In the context of these reactions, the formation of products is impacted by these manners. In zeolites, several acid sites make hydrogen transfer processes more efficient [14, 33, 34]. Crystalline solid acids, like zeolites, are considered to have most of their acid sites in the material's pores [14, 36]. Acidity and other catalyst parameters are linked to these reactions' relative extent, as are the experimental variables used, including reactor type, temperature, and residence period. [21]. Fuel quality and the rate of isomerization are enhanced with catalysts with acidic surfaces and the ability to donate hydrogen ions, increasing the yield of hydrocarbon isomers and improving fuel quality.

Cracking polyolefins is facilitated by catalysts with larger densities and more substantial acid sites. On the other hand, firm acidity and large pore size quickly deactivate the catalyst. It is recommended by literature that polyethylene be pyrolyzed using a catalyst that has low acidity and extended life [31]. Catalysts containing Lewis acid (AlCl_3 , FeCl_3 , TiCl_4 , and TiCl_3) sites, which function as electron pair acceptors, may also be employed in pyrolysis [17]. The catalysts may be evenly distributed in the melted polymer., increasing cracking efficiency while lowering consumption. It is possible to create carbonium ions by removing hydride ions from hydrocarbons using acidic sites on the surfaces of these sorts of catalysts. This process alters the charge distribution in the carbon chain. As a result, the pyrolysis temperature may be reduced, and olefinic and aromatic chemicals can generate more ions due to the catalytic action [38]. Catalyst costs significantly impact process efficiency in catalytic pyrolysis, even if they are well-received [24, 36]. The catalyst's life cycle is shortened by coke production, which is the primary issue with using catalysts in the pyrolysis of plastics [31]. Fig. 2 illustrates a flow chart of catalytic pyrolysis [31].

Fig. 2: A diagram for the catalytic cracking process

3. Materials and Methods

Initially, the reviewers began to seek relevant kinds of literature on staff development. The reviewers employed electronic databases and keyword-searching approaches to discover available conventional and online materials on the topic. Finding and identifying sources was first done as a subject of interest. The primary resources used were Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Academia, and CORE. The Snowball method was also used for a more in-depth study [39]. The World Wide Web search engines were employed to access information from the mentioned sources to discover full-text study publications from online journals. In the first phase, specific keywords were used to identify the relevant studies. The Boolean operator "OR" was used between multiple relevant search results for a wide range of results. Then, to narrow the search results to the most relevant results, the Boolean operator 'AND' was used between multiple keywords, which resulted in more focused records. The PRISMA diagram was prepared (Fig. 3) to provide an overall idea of how the reviewers performed the method [40]. After searching the designated databases and adding records from additional sources, all the search results were compiled into the citation management application Zotero [41]. The duplicate items were removed by sorting the article's digital object identifier (DOI). Each record's title and abstract were read carefully in the second step. The reviewers were

Fig. 3: The PRISMA flow diagram of the study

tasked with determining whether or not the article included information that would be relevant or important to the systematic review. Some items were omitted for each exclusionary criterion. In the third phase, the remaining articles from the title and abstract screening were read entirely. Screening was done to examine whether or not these papers might aid in answering the research questions. After rejecting irrelevant studies in the full-text screen, the procedure reached its fourth and final step, in which it was assessed how many of these studies could be included in a quantitative analysis, also known as a meta-analysis for systematic review.

4. Results and Discussions

The optimal temperature necessary to maximize the amount of liquid oil output in thermal and catalytic pyrolysis has been outlined in Table 1, which provides a summary of the relevant data. According to Table 1, PET and PVC are two forms of plastic that generated a relatively low yield of liquid oil in contrast to other types of plastic. It is important to note that the pyrolysis process is not advised for use with all forms of plastic. In addition, the oil produced by pyrolysis includes chlorinated compounds, which would lead to a decline in the product's quality and harm the environment. According to the findings, the optimal temperature for liquid oil yield in plastic pyrolysis would be 500-550 °C during thermal pyrolysis, whereas using a catalyst during the pyrolysis allowed the optimal temperature to be reduced to 400-450 °C, producing a greater quantity of liquid [43]. Using a catalyst in the production process can potentially increase the output of liquid oil in most plastics. However, polystyrene (PS) was an exception because 97 percent of the oil was produced without catalysts [42]. This case happened because PS deteriorated extremely readily without any catalysts to accelerate the process.

For this reason, polystyrene (PS) turned out to be the ideal material for pyrolysis since it resulted in the most significant quantity of liquid oil production out of all the polymers. Seo et al. highlighted the significance of the catalyst in the pyrolysis process of plastic waste based on their experimental results where low- and high-density polyethylene were subjected to thermal and catalytic pyrolysis using different catalysts [43]. This technique, comprising both thermal and catalytic pyrolysis, yielded pyrolysis oil, carbon black, and gaseous mixes with unique yield characteristics. It has been discovered that thermal pyrolysis may be preferred for producing liquid products, whilst catalytic pyrolysis is favoured for producing gaseous products [43]. The products generated via catalytic pyrolysis have a more concentrated distribution of the total number of carbon atoms, meaning they are more precisely targeted. In addition, the catalytic process shortens the time needed for degradation and reduces the amount of solid waste produced.

Table 1: Summary of research on the pyrolysis of plastics

References	Types of plastics	Reactor	Temperature (°C)	Yield (wt.%)		
				Oil	Gas	Solid
[44]	PET	Batch	500	38.9	52.1	8.9
[45]	HDPE	Semi-batch	400	82.0	16.0	2.0
[46]	HDPE	Batch	450	74.5	5.8	19.7
[47]	PVC	Fixed bed	500	12.3	87.7	0
[47]	LDPE	Batch	430	75.6	8.2	7.5
[32]	PP	Batch	380	80.1	6.6	13.3
[48]	PP	Semi-batch	450	92.3	4.1	3.6
[45]	PS	Semi-batch	400	90.0	6.0	4.0
[42]	PS	Pressurized Batch	425	97.0	2.5	0.0

5. Conclusion

This article provides an in-depth analysis of the importance of plastic waste management and explores the potential applicability of pyrolysis for its beneficial utilization. The utilization of waste plastics pyrolysis offers an alternative fuel source that is a worthy endeavour from both an environmental and economic standpoint. The preference for pyrolysis is primarily attributed to its superior capacity to efficiently transform plastic waste into commercially viable forms such as liquid oil, gaseous substances, and char, maximizing energy conversion. Product choice flexibility can be achieved by appropriately modifying associated factors. Using thermal pyrolysis to recycle waste plastics offers various benefits over other recycling technologies.

On the other hand, Conversion to liquid at lower temperatures using catalysts is a more viable option. A significant distinction between thermal and catalytic pyrolysis is that the oil produced in the presence of a catalyst has a greater volume and a lower boiling range than the oil produced without the catalyst. The gasoline or kerosene may be mixed with the whole pyrolytic oil. Therefore, utilization of catalytic pyrolysis holds significant importance from both economic and environmental perspectives.

Nevertheless, further investigation is required prior to the utilization of pyrolytic oil as a viable liquid fuel or as a feedback mechanism. The catalytic method can reduce the operating temperature and increase liquid oil production for most polymers using the correct catalyst choice. The quantity of plastic waste in each country has reached millions of metric tons. Using pyrolysis, plastic waste management will become more effective, less landfill capacity will be required, and plastic pollution will decrease. In addition, pyrolysis, as a process for converting plastic waste into usable energy, decreases the reliance on fossil fuels as non-renewable energy. Simultaneously addressing the energy need limiting the rise in greenhouse gas emissions is also possible.

References

1. Deshmukh S, Mokadam P (2017) LIQUID FUEL EXTRACTION FROM PLASTIC WASTE
2. Plastics Industry Association | Better Industry. Better World. <https://www.plasticsindustry.org/>. Accessed 11 Jul 2022
3. Visual Feature | Beat Plastic Pollution. <http://unep.org/interactive/beat-plastic-pollution/>. Accessed 22 Oct 2023
4. Martin C, Young CA, Valluzzi L, Duarte CM (2022) Ocean sediments as the global sink for marine micro- and mesoplastics. *Limnol Oceanogr Letters* 7:235–243. <https://doi.org/10.1002/lol2.10257>
5. admin (2019) Why plastics can be garbage for the climate. In: Yale Climate Connections. <http://yaleclimateconnections.org/2019/08/how-plastics-contribute-to-climate-change/>. Accessed 14 Jul 2022
6. Mendes MR, Aramaki T, Hanaki K (2004) Comparison of the environmental impact of incineration and landfilling in São Paulo City as determined by LCA. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 41:47–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2003.08.003>
7. Blazsó M, Jakab E (2007) Pyrolysis 2006. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 79:1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2007.02.005>
8. Jayanthi J, Kamalakar D, Rao LN (2015) Conversion of waste plastics into alternative fuel. *International Journal of Engineering Science and Research Technology* 4:195–201
9. Dianta Mustofa Kamal, Fuad Zainuri (2015) Green Product of Liquid Fuel from Plastic Waste by Pyrolysis at 900 °C. *JEPE* 9:. <https://doi.org/10.17265/1934-8975/2015.01.004>
10. Sharuddin SDA, Abnisa F, Daud WMAW, Aroua MK (2018) Pyrolysis of plastic waste for liquid fuel production as prospective energy resource. *IOP Conf Ser: Mater Sci Eng* 334:012001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/334/1/012001>
11. Mathur K Extraction of Pyrolysis oil from Waste Plastics. 03:4
12. Arunkumar B, Nataraj C (2017) Conversion of waste plastic into fuel oil in the presence of bentonite as a catalyst. *Int Res J Eng Technol* 4:114–119
13. Mastral JF, Berruero C, Ceamanos J (2007) Theoretical prediction of product distribution of the pyrolysis of high density polyethylene. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 80:427–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2006.07.009>
14. Panda AK, Singh RK, Mishra DK (2010) Thermolysis of waste plastics to liquid fuel: A suitable method for plastic waste management and manufacture of value added products—A world prospective. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 14:233–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2009.07.005>

15. Achilias DS, Roupakias C, Megalokonomos P, Lappas AA, Antonakou EV (2007) Chemical recycling of plastic wastes made from polyethylene (LDPE and HDPE) and polypropylene (PP). *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 149:536–542. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2007.06.076>
16. Marcilla A, Beltrán MI, Navarro R (2009) Thermal and catalytic pyrolysis of polyethylene over HZSM5 and HUSY zeolites in a batch reactor under dynamic conditions. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental* 86:78–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2008.07.026>
17. Kaminsky W, Zorriquetta I-JN (2007) Catalytical and thermal pyrolysis of polyolefins. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 79:368–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2006.11.005>
18. Arabiourrutia M, Elordi G, Lopez G, Borsella E, Bilbao J, Olazar M (2012) Characterization of the waxes obtained by the pyrolysis of polyolefin plastics in a conical spouted bed reactor. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 94:230–237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2011.12.012>
19. Guohua L, Suto T, Yasu S, Kato K (2000) Catalytic degradation of high density polyethylene and polypropylene into liquid fuel in a powder-particle fluidized bed. *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 70:97–102. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(00\)00095-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(00)00095-1)
20. Al-Haj Ibrahim H (2020) Introductory Chapter: Pyrolysis. In: Al- Haj Ibrahim H (ed) *Recent Advances in Pyrolysis*. IntechOpen
21. Kaminsky W, Scheirs J (2006) *Feedstock recycling and pyrolysis of waste plastics*. J. Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ
22. Ghosh SK (2019) *Energy Recovery Processes from Wastes*. Springer Nature
23. Miskolczi N, Angyal A, Bartha L, Valkai I (2009) Fuels by pyrolysis of waste plastics from agricultural and packaging sectors in a pilot scale reactor. *Fuel Processing Technology* 90:1032–1040. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2009.04.019>
24. Lin H-T, Huang M-S, Luo J-W, Lin L-H, Lee C-M, Ou K-L (2010) Hydrocarbon fuels produced by catalytic pyrolysis of hospital plastic wastes in a fluidizing cracking process. *Fuel Processing Technology* 91:1355–1363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2010.03.016>
25. Lopez-Uribebarrenechea A, de Marco I, Caballero BM, Laresgoiti MF, Adrados A (2012) Catalytic stepwise pyrolysis of packaging plastic waste. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 96:54–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2012.03.004>
26. Lin Y-H, Yang M-H (2008) Tertiary recycling of polyethylene waste by fluidised-bed reactions in the presence of various cracking catalysts. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 83:101–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2008.06.004>
27. Liu W, hu C, Yang Y, Tong D, Li G, Zhu L (2010) Influence of ZSM-5 zeolite on the pyrolytic intermediates from the co-pyrolysis of pubescens and LDPE. *Energy Conversion and Management - ENERGMANAGE* 51:1025–1032. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2009.12.005>
28. Murata K, Brebu M, Sakata Y (2010) The effect of silica–alumina catalysts on degradation of polyolefins by a continuous flow reactor. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 89:30–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2010.05.002>
29. Dobó Z, Kecsmár G, Jakab Z, Nagy G *Production of Liquid Hydrocarbons from Plastic Wastes*
30. Fahim I, Mohsen O, ElKayaly D (2021) Production of Fuel from Plastic Waste: A Feasible Business. *Polymers* 13:915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym13060915>
31. Scheirs J (2006) Overview of Commercial Pyrolysis Processes for Waste Plastics. In: Scheirs J, Kaminsky W (eds) *Overview of Commercial Pyrolysis Processes for Waste Plastics*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Chichester, UK, pp 381–433
32. (1999) Degradation of polyethylene and polypropylene into fuel oil by using solid acid and non-acid catalysts — Okayama University. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 51:21
33. Mastral J, Berruete C, Gea M, Ceamanos J (2006) Catalytic degradation of high density polyethylene over nanocrystalline HZSM-5 zeolite. *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 91:3330–3338. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polymdegradstab.2006.06.009>
34. Miskolczi N, Bartha L (2008) Investigation of hydrocarbon fractions from waste plastic recycling by FTIR, GC, EDXRFS and SEC techniques. *Journal of Biochemical and Biophysical Methods* 70:1247–1253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbbm.2007.05.005>
35. Serrano DP, Aguado J, Escola JM, Rodríguez JM (2005) Influence of nanocrystalline HZSM-5 external surface on the catalytic cracking of polyolefins. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 74:353–360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2004.11.037>
36. Muzzy DJ CATALYTIC PYROLYSIS OF POLYOLEFINS. 217
37. Jerzak W, Gao N, Kalemba-Rec I, Magdziarz A (2021) Catalytic intermediate pyrolysis of post-extraction rapeseed meal by reusing ZSM-5 and Zeolite Y catalysts. *Catalysis Today*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cattod.2021.10.023>

38. Singh S, Wu C, Williams PT (2012) Pyrolysis of waste materials using TGA-MS and TGA-FTIR as complementary characterisation techniques. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 94:99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2011.11.011>
39. Naderifar M, Goli H, Ghaljaie F (2017) Snowball Sampling: A Purposeful Method of Sampling in Qualitative Research. *Strides Dev Med Educ* 14:. <https://doi.org/10.5812/sdme.67670>
40. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, Shamseer L, Tetzlaff JM, Akl EA, Brennan SE, Chou R, Glanville J, Grimshaw JM, Hróbjartsson A, Lalu MM, Li T, Loder EW, Mayo-Wilson E, McDonald S, McGuinness LA, Stewart LA, Thomas J, Tricco AC, Welch VA, Whiting P, Moher D (2021) The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
41. Zotero | Your personal research assistant. <https://www.zotero.org/>. Accessed 11 Jul 2022
42. Onwudili JA, Insura N, Williams PT (2009) Composition of products from the pyrolysis of polyethylene and polystyrene in a closed batch reactor: Effects of temperature and residence time. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 86:293–303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2009.07.008>
43. Seo Y-H, Lee K-H, Shin D-H (2003) Investigation of catalytic degradation of high-density polyethylene by hydrocarbon group type analysis. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis* 70:383–398. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-2370\(02\)00186-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-2370(02)00186-9)
44. FakhrHoseini SM, Dastanian M (2013) Predicting Pyrolysis Products of PE, PP, and PET Using NRTL Activity Coefficient Model. *Journal of Chemistry* 2013:e487676. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/487676>
45. Thermal and thermo-catalytic degradation of high-density polyethylene waste - ScienceDirect. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0165237004000634>. Accessed 12 Jul 2022
46. Mohd. Wasif Quadri, Devendra Dohare, Shri Govindram Seksaria Institute of Technology and Science Indore (2020) A Study to Optimise Plastic to Fuel Technology-A Review. *IJERT* V9:IJERTV9IS040137. <https://doi.org/10.17577/IJERTV9IS040137>
47. Uddin MA, Koizumi K, Murata K, Sakata Y (1997) Thermal and catalytic degradation of structurally different types of polyethylene into fuel oil. *Polymer Degradation and Stability* 56:37–44. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910\(96\)00191-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-3910(96)00191-7)
48. Abbas-Abadi MS, Haghghi MN, Yeganeh H, McDonald AG (2014) Evaluation of pyrolysis process parameters on polypropylene degradation products. *Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis Complete*:272–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2014.05.023>